

Information Modelling for Building Automantion: towards for the integration of BIM tools in Robotic Fabrication and 3DCP process

ADRIANO APARECIDO FRANCHINI

Supervisors:

Bruno Figueiredo

School of Architecture, Art and Design, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Paulo Jorge de Sousa Cruz

School of Architecture, Art and Design, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Pedro Andrade

Grupo CASAIS, Braga, Portugal

Abstract

In the coming years, there will be significant challenges to improving environmental sustainability and the demand for reducing the consumption of natural resources and energy. These are two of the significant issues faced by professionals in the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) industry. To address this, integrating Building Information Modelling (BIM) with advanced manufacturing technologies, such as 3D concrete printing (3DCP), offers innovative solutions to these challenges. The aim is to improve efficiency, productivity, and integration of the information flow between project phases and stakeholders. This study explores the integration of BIM with 3DCP and uses these technologies in prefabrication construction to enhance design flexibility, construction efficiency, and sustainability in the AEC field. The research focuses on using prefabricated façade panels, a hybrid system of wood and concrete currently used by Blufab company, as a case study to demonstrate the practical application of these technologies. The investigation developed a framework for

exploring the individual characteristics of these technologies from the design phases to the implementation of a prototype.

A literature review analysis was conducted to understand the current applications of BIM and 3DCP in construction. Then, the dissertation will continue developing the methodology and workflow for the implementation process. This corresponded to the generation of a Computational Model, Robot programming, and Integration with the BIM environment, and the prototype was tested to validate the feasibility of the proposed approach.

The findings demonstrate that integrating BIM with 3DCP significantly improves design flexibility, construction efficiency, and information flow. The use of prefabricated façade panels reduced construction time and improved sustainability performance. The developed workflow facilitated better collaboration among stakeholders and increased the interoperability of digital tools in the construction process.

This dissertation research highlights the potential of BIM, 3DCP, and prefabricated façade panel integration in advancing sustainable and efficient construction practices. The approach offers a design solution and computational optimization for construction challenges, contributing to the AEC industry's digital transformation and providing an opportunity for further innovation and development. Future research should explore optimizing these technologies to enhance their applicability in diverse construction projects for greater productivity and innovation.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/so3AE40xPiA>

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